

TDABC, A Practical Solution to Calculating the Cost of Revenue for MSMEs in the Convection Service Sector: A Case Study on MSME "XYZ" in Indonesia

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Abstract: Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play an important role in supporting Indonesia's economic growth. One of the success factors for SMEs is the accurate calculation of the cost of product. This study aimed to apply the Time-Driven Activity Based Costing (TDABC) method in calculating the cost of convection products of "XYZ", a small-medium enterprise (SME) located on Jl. Raya Ragunan, Pasar Minggu, South Jakarta, Indonesia. The data obtained and processed were the data for one year, which included data on sales, costs, number of employees, operating hours and various activities required to support the production and sales activities. The results showed that TDABC could be applied to MSME "XYZ", could accurately and comprehensively calculate the cost of revenue of each type of product (cost to make and sell). The application of TDABC also allowed MSME "XYZ" to gain insights into the effectiveness of the working time of its employees.

Keywords: convection, costing, tailor, TDABC, time-driven activity based costing

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play an important role in supporting Indonesia's economic growth. According to data from the Indonesian Association of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Akumindo), MSMEs contributed 65% to state revenue and 96% to the employment sector [1]. Data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs [2] showed that the contribution of MSMEs was 61.07% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), absorbing 97% of the total workforce and 60.42% of total investment in 2018. Data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs in 2019 showed that the MSME sector had a 99% market share, absorbed 96.92% of the workforce, and contributed to 57.1% of GDP. [3].

The number of MSMEs in Indonesia has increased every year. Based on data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs [2], in 2017 there were 62.93 million MSMEs, increasing to 64.2 million MSMEs in 2018 and increasing again to 65.47 million MSMEs in 2019. Data from the Capital Investment Coordinating Board (BKPM) [4] showed that there were 353,478 new micro-enterprises that applied for a Business Permit Number (NIB) in October 2020. In the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic, MSMEs need a helping hand, in the form of financing or capital, from various parties. According to Bank Indonesia records, in 2022 the potential for financing the MSME sector is Rp 1,605 trillion [3].

Although the number has increased every year, the development of MSMEs tends to be hampered. One of the causes is an error in setting the selling price [5]. The results of the initial observations on MSMEs engaged in services showed that MSME owners only made use of their experience and habits in setting the selling price of their products or services, and disregarded the calculation of the cost of product in accordance with accounting rules. As a result, MSME entrepreneurs were not able to determine whether their MSMEs were making a profit or actually experiencing a loss. Errors in the calculation of the cost of product will result in inaccurate calculation of the selling price of a product or service. It can be concluded that an accurate cost of product is one of the factors that play an important role in the success of running an MSME business. With an accurate cost of product, the calculation of profit (loss) and inventory value becomes accurate as well.

Currently, traditional costing (volume based costing) still dominates the majority of business activities when calculating the cost of product. This method can produce an accurate basic calculation when the products are not diverse (thus consuming relatively the same resources) and the overhead costs are relatively small.

Changes in consumer tastes and needs that are growing rapidly today urge businesses to adapt by making various efforts to fulfill the demands of their customers or consumers. The differences in consumer tastes and needs have an impact on the use of different resources, both in terms of quality and quantity. Likewise with the composition of production costs. In addition, changes that occur in production methods, information technology, the quality of human resources, and so on also have an impact on the composition of production costs, from being dominated by material and labor costs whose changes depend on the quantity of production, to becoming increasingly dominated by overhead costs whose changes are no longer correlated with production volume. With the changes, if businesses still use the traditional method to calculate the cost of their products, it will result in an inaccurate calculation of the cost of product. This will have an impact on the calculation of operating profit (loss) and the value of the inventory.

A method of calculating cost of product known as Activity Based Costing (ABC) was introduced [6]. The ABC method focuses on assigning costs based on the pattern of resource consumption by the product. This method assumes that the activity consumes resources and the product consumes the activity. Thus, in the ABC method, the first stage is to assign costs from resources to activities, the second stage is to assign activity costs to products or other cost objects (services/departments). Activities in the ABC method are classified into four categories, namely unit-level activities, batch-level activities, product-level activities, and facility-level activities. In practice, there are various obstacles in the application of the ABC method, such as requiring large costs in the interview and survey process, producing data that are expensive to store, process, and report, and the difficulty in updating the method to accommodate changing circumstances.

Then, a new approach, namely Time-Driven Activity Based Costing (TDABC) as a solution to various obstacles in the application of the ABC method was introduced [6]. The TDABC method eliminates the interview and survey process to allocate resource costs to activities and then to the product, resulting in calculations that are easier, cheaper, and more accurate than the ABC method.

In TDABC, the assignment of costs to activities is carried out directly using time estimates. This makes it easier for businesses to determine the ratio of consumption of activities during the production process, which can be measured and estimated by the amount of time. The advantages of TDABC include building accurate models easily and quickly, integrating with available data from Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM), providing information on process efficiency and capacity utilization, helping in predicting resource demand, providing fast and inexpensive model maintenance, helping business or industrial activities with high complexity, calculating the cost of product which include production costs and operating costs (cost to make and sell) accurately, and providing information to identify problems. As such, the TDABC method has the potential to be applied to all business activities. TDABC can be applied to all organizations that have various product or customer types, transaction data, large overhead costs and a process that can be standardized. The implementation of the TDABC model only requires a system that can track transaction data that can be exported into the equation of time. The data can be obtained through the use of spreadsheet packages such as Microsoft Excel and Lotus 1-2-3 [6]. Various research results on the application of TDABC show that TDABC produces a more accurate calculation of cost of product [7][8], and can reduce the complexity of cost measurement [9].

Thus, TDABC can also be applied to business activities engaged in services. In general, products and consumers in the service sector vary widely so that the resources consumed by each service product are also very varied. In addition, the costs that dominate business activities in the service sector are overhead costs, the majority of which are not correlated with the quantity or volume of production. Service products also vary in the length of time it takes to complete a product. Likewise with human resources. Human resources who work on products often also carry out operational activities. These various conditions make TDABC very suitable to be applied in the service business sector. TDABC is able to provide a more accurate cost calculation than ABC. TDABC can identify unused capacity, enable operational improvements, and detect non-value added activities [10].

An example of calculating the cost of service activities to reduce the complexity of cost measurement in service companies using the TDABC method was provided [9]. Some of the advantages of applying the TDABC method in service companies were summarized [11]. First, if TDABC is applied based on the equation of time and enterprise resource planning (ERP) system, the method is easier to implement and maintain than the ABC method. Second, TDABC does not promise calculation accuracy, but provides accurate cost data and alignment of product costs and customer costs with resource consumption. Third, medium-sized companies can implement TDABC to allocate support costs to products, customers, and orders with the help of an ERP system. Although TDABC is not recognized as Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) for financial reporting purposes, it is useful in the decision-making process and can be

applied at the product, process, and operations control levels. The TDABC method can calculate costs in more detail, such as transaction costs, invoices, orders, order lines, shipments, and shipping lines. With the TDABC method, the total time is calculated based on the time equation for each recorded cost object [12]. The application of TDABC at Metro Health, which was engaged in health services [7], showed that TDABC could produce a more accurate cost per visit by considering the complexity of each visit. TDABC can also develop a database system that can be used to identify groups or departments that are less resource efficient for process improvement efforts. A case study on the application of TDABC at hotels in Turkey [8] showed that some customer segments that were not profitable under the conventional ABC method became profitable after implementing TDABC. The study also revealed that TDABC could be used to analyze problems, so that all available resources could be used to improve overall hotel performance. A case study, also on hotels [13], showed that TDABC could calculate the level of cost of capacity more accurately and flexibly. Research on the application of TDABC at airports in Italy [14] showed that the TDABC method was useful for supporting capacity management as well as fostering the relationship between costing systems, strategy and operations. Research on the application of TDABC [15] in Information Technology (IT) companies showed that TDABC is an effective tool to identify processes that cost a lot and provide useful information for making critical decisions about cost control. Research on the implementation of TDABC in domestic electronics and engineering companies [16] showed that TDABC provided cost information that was more accurate, easy to maintain, and integrated with data available in enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems. From the various research results, it can be concluded that TDABC can be applied to the service business sector, both large and small scale.

Based on the many benefits that can be obtained through the application of TDABC, we conducted a study to apply TDABC in calculating the cost of revenue (for service companies) of MSME "XYZ" that was engaged in tailoring or convection services. By using TDABC, we hoped that the calculation of cost of revenue could be more accurate as all cost elements the resources used to produce and sell products were taken into account, no longer relying on experience or following competitors' prices.

II. METHOD

We conducted surveys and interviews for one month at UMKM "XYZ", an SME located on Jl. Raya Ragunan, Pasar Minggu, South Jakarta, Indonesia. In-depth interviews were conducted with the owner, cashier, and employees. We conducted these surveys and interviews to collect the data required in calculating the cost of revenue using TDABC. The data consisted of operational time, number of employees, types of products, various main activities and supporting activities in the process of providing convection services, estimated time required for each activity, sales data and costs incurred in the process of providing services for one year.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data obtained from the owner and surveys on-site, there were 10 types of products, namely suit, blazer, PDH uniform, safari, shirt, blouse, trousers, skirt, dress and kebaya. The data of costs for one year consisted of direct material costs and indirect costs. The various types of direct material costs required by each type of product per unit are presented in table 1. Fabric was not included as part of direct material costs as the customers prepared the fabric themselves. Indirect costs are costs that are used jointly by all products and are presented in table 2. There were 16 main activities and one supporting activity, which are presented in table 3.

Table 1. Direct Material Cost Requirements per Product Unit

No.	Product	Direct Material	Requirements	Unit	Cost per unit	Cost per Unit (Rp)
1	Jacket	Lining fabric	1.5	meter	24,000	52,070
		Ring	2	pcs	2,500	
		Padding	2	pcs	1,500	
		Button	8	pcs	3,000	
		Embroidery	1	pcs	5,000	
		Cover	1	pcs	11,000	
		Hanger	1	pcs	5,000	
		Label	1	pcs	70	
2	Blazer	Lining fabric	1.5	meter	24,000	

		Ring	2	pcs	2,500	
		Cotton	2	pcs	1,500	
		Button	8	pcs	3,000	
		Cover	1	pcs	11,000	
		Hanger	1	pcs	5,000	
		Label	1	pcs	70	47,070
3	PDH uniform	Lining fabric	1.3	meter	15,600	
		Button	10	pcs	1,600	
		Zip	1	pcs	1,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	18,770
4	Safari	Lining fabric	1.5	meter	18,000	
		Button	10	pcs	1,600	
		Padding	2	pcs	4,500	
		Zip	1	pcs	1,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	25,670
5	Shirt	Lining fabric	1.4	meter	15,400	
		Button	1	lusin	2,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	17,970
6	Blouse	Lining fabric	1.4	meter	15,400	
		Zip	1	pcs	7,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	22,970
7	Trousers	Zip	1	pcs	1,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	1,570
8	Skirt	Zip	1	pcs	1,500	
		Lining fabric	1.5	meter	16,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	18,070
9	Dress	Zip	1	pcs	7,500	
		Label	1	pcs	70	7,570
10	Kebaya	Embroidery	1	pcs	25,000	
		Dorset button	2	dozen	12,000	
		Label	1	pcs	70	37,070

Table 2. Indirect Cost for One Year

No.	Indirect Cost Type	Total Cost (Rp)
1	Indirect material	77,022,800
2	Salaries and allowances	
	Cashier	26,000,000
	Production coordinator	52,000,000
	Measure and cut	91,000,000
	Tailor	260,000,000
	Jacket tailor	32,500,000
	Finishing	78,000,000
	Ironing	26,000,000
3	Production supplies	5,213,000
4	Operational supplies	1,354,000
5	Electricity	9,600,000
6	Telephone	1,800,000
7	Depreciation of Fixed Assets: - Mechanical equipment	3,572,657
	- Manual equipment	2,718,750
	- Building	22,500,000
8	Machine maintenance	1,697,000
9	Building maintenance	5,000,000

10	Property tax	450,000
11	Others	7,128,500
Total		703,556,707

Steps to calculate the cost of revenue with TDABC

1. Identifying primary and support activities (table 3)
2. Determining indirect cost consumption ratio (%) per activity (table 4)
3. Calculating the indirect costs consumed by each activity (table 5)
4. Calculating the rate per activity. In calculating the rate per activity, the following two steps were required:
 - a. Calculating the time capacity based on the time consumption ratio of each activity. Time capacity is the total working time of all employees for one year. We referred to Ministerial Decree No. KEP-102/MEN/IV/2004 Article 8 paragraph (2) concerning overtime work and overtime pay is 173 hours for one month. The working time used effectively in the process of providing convection services was 60% of the total working time for one year. The remaining 40% of working time was rest time, idle time when there is no order, and waiting time for the preparation of materials and equipment. Then the effective working time of one employee was = 173 hours x 12 months x 60% = 1,245 hours rounded down to 1,200 hours/employee/year. Rounding down 1,245 hours to 1,200 hours was done by taking into account the presence of employees who took additional leave and were absent due to illness or absenteeism. Thus, the total effective working time of all employees for one year was: 1,200 hours x 17 people = 20,400 hours. Then, we calculated the estimated time required to perform each activity (table 6). The next step was converting the time consumption of each activity into minutes (table 7).
 - b. Calculating the rate per activity. The rate per activity was calculated by dividing the total indirect costs of each activity by the time consumed by each activity (table 8).
5. Calculating the cost of revenue. In calculating the cost of revenue, the following two steps were carried out:
 - a. Assigning indirect costs to cost of revenue by multiplying the rate per activity by the time consumption required for each unit of cost of revenue. Especially for uniform products that are processed in large quantities (in bulk), the time consumption is presented in table 9.
 - b. Adding up direct material costs and indirect costs to obtain cost of revenue per unit for ordinary products (table 10), while the calculation of cost of revenue per unit for uniform products is presented in table 11.

Table 3. Primary Activities and Support Activities

No	Activity	Description
1	Accepting order	The cashier takes orders over the phone or the customer comes in person to the store. The cashier determines the estimated time for completion of the order and the customer approves it. The cashier hands a copy of the order note to the customer. The order is recorded in the order list. Execution is based on which order comes first. Order in large quantities, such as making uniforms, requires a down payment, the remaining payment is paid off after the order is completed received by the customer.
2	Designing clothes	The measurer discusses the desired clothing design with the customer, draws the clothing design, the concept of the stitch pattern, the variation of the stitch, the collar model, the shape and placement of the pockets, the placement of the type and color of buttons, the addition of other materials such as lining, accessories, etc. The measurer also provides recommendations regarding the brand and color number of the fabric to customers who have not prepared the fabric so that customers can buy their own fabric to be sewn.
3	Designing uniform	The uniform design according to the customer's wishes is carried out at the customer's place. This activity includes travel time to and from the customer's place.
4	Measuring	The Measure & Cut does the fitting so that the clothes fit the customer's measurement.
5	Measuring at the customer's place	For orders in large quantities such as uniforms, the measuring department will take measurements at the customer's place.
6	Preparing materials & equipment	The production coordinator calculates and purchases the materials and sewing supplies needed.
7	Making patterns	The pattern person draws the pattern on the cloth using chalk according to the design and size.

8	Cutting cloth	The cutter cuts the fabric one by one following the pattern that has been made. Then it is handed over to the overlocker along with the order number and the design of the clothes.
9	Overlocking	The fabric is overlocked using an overlock sewing machine and the thread whose color is the same as the color of the fabric.
10	Sewing	The sewing process is done by using a sewing machine to become finished clothes.
11	Finishing	The finisher attaches buttons to the clothes, accessories, and sewing. Then the finisher checks the stitches and removes the remaining thread in the stitching of the clothes.
12	Ironing	Ironing the inside and outside of clothes using a steam iron to lock creases in clothes, apply hard fabrics, and keep clothes neat and wrinkle-free.
13	Packaging	For jacket, it will be packaged using a special jacket cover. All finished clothes will be hung on the order rack along with a description of the order number and customer information.
14	Taking order	The cashier contacts the customer to take their order by handing over a copy of the order note.
15	Adjusting	Customers who have complaints about after trying the clothes can request for an adjustment.
16	Making a payment	Customers who have no complaints can take their clothes by paying off the total payment or the remaining payment and getting a receipt.
17	Support activities	Carrying out maintenance of production machines, cleaning the scraps, tidying up the equipment and supplies used, and cleaning the production room.

No.	Indirect Cost	Activity Type (%)																
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
1	Indirect material									2	90	4				4		
2	Salaries and allowances																	
	Cashier	25					20								25		25	5
	Production coordinator		5	5	5	5	20	5	5	5	25	5	5			10		
	Measure and cut		15	10	15	10		25	25									
	Tailor										80					15		5
	Jacket tailor										80					15		5
	Finishing									35		60						5
	Ironing												75	20				5
3	Production supplies				2	2		40	4	10	12	16	4			10		
4	Operational supplies	50															50	
5	Electricity	5	5		5		5	5	5	10	15	10	5	5	5	10	5	5
6	Telephone	40					20								40			
7	Depreciation of Fixed Asset																	
	Mechanical equipment	2					2			10	65	2	5		2	10		2
	Manual Equipment	5	5		5			5	10	5	30	5	5	10	5	5	5	
	Building	5	5		5		5	5	10	10	20	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
8	Machine maintenance									5	85	5				5		
9	Building maintenance	5	5		5		5	5	10	10	20	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
10	Property tax	5	5		5		5	5	10	10	20	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
11	Others			5		5									60			30

Table 4. Indirect Cost Consumption Ratio per Activity (%)

Table 5. Indirect Cost Consumption per Activity (Rp)

No.	Indirect Cost	Activity Type																	Total Cost
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
1	Indirect material	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,540,456	69,320,520	3,080,912	-	-	-	3,080,912	-	-	77,022,800
2	Salaries and allowances	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Cashier	6,500,000	-	-	-	-	5,200,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6,500,000	-	6,500,000	1,300,000	26,000,000
	Production coordinator	-	2,600,000	2,600,000	2,600,000	2,600,000	10,400,000	2,600,000	2,600,000	2,600,000	13,000,000	2,600,000	2,600,000	-	-	5,200,000	-	-	52,000,000
	Measure and cut	-	13,650,000	9,100,000	13,650,000	9,100,000	-	22,750,000	22,750,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	91,000,000
	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	208,000,000	-	-	-	-	39,000,000	-	13,000,000	260,000,000
	Jacket tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	26,000,000	-	-	-	-	4,875,000	-	1,625,000	32,500,000
	Finishing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	27,300,000	-	46,800,000	-	-	-	-	-	3,900,000	78,000,000
	Ironing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	19,500,000	5,200,000	-	-	-	1,300,000	26,000,000
3	Production supplies	-	-	-	104,260	104,260	-	2,085,200	208,520	521,300	625,560	834,080	208,520	-	-	521,300	-	-	5,213,000
4	Operational supplies	677,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	677,000	-	1,354,000
5	Electricity	480,000	480,000	-	480,000	-	480,000	480,000	480,000	960,000	1,440,000	960,000	480,000	480,000	480,000	960,000	480,000	480,000	9,600,000
6	Telephone	720,000	-	-	-	-	360,000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	720,000	-	-	-	1,800,000
7	Depr. of Fixed Asset	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Mechanical equipment	71,453	-	-	-	-	71,453	-	-	357,266	2,322,227	71,453	178,633	-	71,453	357,266	-	71,453	3,572,657
	Manual Equipment	135,938	135,938	-	135,938	-	-	135,938	271,875	135,938	815,625	135,938	135,938	271,875	135,938	135,938	135,938	-	2,718,750
	Building	1,125,000	1,125,000	-	1,125,000	-	1,125,000	1,125,000	2,250,000	2,250,000	4,500,000	1,125,000	1,125,000	1,125,000	1,125,000	1,125,000	1,125,000	1,125,000	22,500,000
8	Machine maintenance	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	84,850	1,442,450	84,850	-	-	-	84,850	-	-	1,697,000
9	Building maintenance	250,000	250,000	-	250,000	-	250,000	250,000	500,000	500,000	1,000,000	250,000	250,000	250,000	250,000	250,000	250,000	250,000	5,000,000
10	Property tax	22,500	22,500	-	22,500	-	22,500	22,500	45,000	45,000	90,000	22,500	22,500	22,500	22,500	22,500	22,500	22,500	450,000
11	Others	-	-	356,425	-	356,425	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,277,100	-	-	-	2,138,550	7,128,500
Total Cost (Rp)		9,981,891	18,263,438	12,056,425	18,367,698	12,160,685	17,908,953	29,448,638	29,105,395	36,294,809	328,556,382	55,964,733	24,500,590	11,626,475	9,304,891	55,612,765	9,190,438	25,212,503	703,556,707

No.	Employee																		Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
1	Cashier	300	-	-	-	-	240	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	300	-	300	60	1,200
2	Production coordinator	-	60	60	60	60	240	60	60	60	300	60	60	-	-	120	-	-	1,200
3	Measure & cut	-	180	120	180	120	-	300	300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,200	
4	Measure & cut	-	180	120	180	120	-	300	300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,200	
5	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
6	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
7	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
8	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
9	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
10	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
11	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
12	Tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
13	Jacket tailor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	960	-	-	-	-	180	-	1,200	
14	Finishing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	420	-	720	-	-	-	-	-	1,200	
15	Finishing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	420	-	720	-	-	-	-	-	1,200	
16	Finishing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	420	-	720	-	-	-	-	-	1,200	
17	Finishing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	900	240	-	-	-	1,200	
Total		300	420	300	420	300	480	660	660	1,320	8,940	2,220	960	240	300	1,740	300	840	20,400

Table 6. Estimate and Distribution of Time to Each Activity (hours)

No.	Activity	Time Consumption	
		Hours	Minutes
1	Accepting order	300	18,000
2	Designing clothes	420	25,200
3	Designing uniform	300	18,000
4	Measuring	420	25,200
5	Measuring at the customer's place	300	18,000
6	Preparing materials and equipment	480	28,800
7	Making patterns	660	39,600
8	Cutting cloth	660	39,600
9	Overlocking	1,320	79,200
10	Sewing	8,940	536,400
11	Finishing	2,220	133,200
12	Ironing	960	57,600
13	Packaging	240	14,400
14	Taking order	300	18,000
15	Adjusting	1,740	104,400
16	Making a payment	300	18,000
17	Support activities	840	50,400
Total		20,400	1,224,000

Table 7. Time Consumption per Activity

Table 8. Rate per Activity

No.	Activity	Indirect Cost (Rp)	Time Consumption (Minutes)	Rate per Activity (Rp/Minutes)
1	Accepting order	9,981,891	18,000	555
2	Designing clothes	18,263,438	25,200	725
3	Designing uniform	12,056,425	18,000	670
4	Measuring	18,367,698	25,200	729
5	Measuring at the customer's place	12,160,685	18,000	676
6	Preparing materials and equipment	17,908,953	28,800	622
7	Making patterns	29,448,638	39,600	744
8	Cutting cloth	29,105,395	39,600	735
9	Overlocking	36,294,809	79,200	458
10	Sewing	328,556,382	536,400	613
11	Finishing	55,964,733	133,200	420
12	Ironing	24,500,590	57,600	425
13	Packaging	11,626,475	14,400	807
14	Taking order	9,304,891	18,000	517
15	Adjusting	55,612,765	104,400	533
16	Making a payment	9,190,438	18,000	511
17	Support activities	25,212,503	50,400	500
Total		703,556,707	1,224,000	

Table 9. Time Consumption of Uniform Product in Bulk (Minutes)

No.	Activity	Uniform Type							
		PDH Uniform		Safari		Shirt		Trousers	
		Time	Unit	Time	Unit	Time	Unit	Time	Unit
1	Batch :								
	Accepting order	10	50	10	50	10	50	10	50
	Designing uniform	40	50	40	50	40	50	40	50
	Taking order	10	50	10	50	10	50	10	50
	Making a payment	10	50	10	50	10	50	10	50
	Support activities	30	50	30	50	30	50	30	50
Total Time		100		100		100		100	
2	Unit :								
	Measuring	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
	Preparing materials and supplies	10	1	10	1	10	1	5	1
	Making patterns	15	1	15	1	15	1	10	1
	Cutting cloth	10	1	10	1	10	1	5	1
	Overlocking	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
	Sewing	60	1	60	1	50	1	25	1
	Finishing	5	1	5	1	5	1	2	1
	Ironing	15	1	15	1	15	1	10	1
	Packaging	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Adjusting	25	1	25	1	20	1	10	1
Total Time		151		151		136		78	

Table 10. Calculation of Cost of Revenue per Unit with TDABC

No.	Cost Type	Rate	Product																			
			Jacket		Blazer		PDH Uniform		Safari		Shirt		Blouse		Trousers		Skirt		Dress		Kebaya	
			Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp	Time	Rp
1	Direct Cost (Rp)		52,070		47,070		18,770		25,670		17,970		22,970		1,570		18,070		7,570		37,070	
2	Activity :																					
	Accepting order	555	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775	5	2,775
	Designing clothes	725	15	10,875	10	7,250	5	3,625	10	7,250	5	3,625	10	7,250	5	3,625	5	3,625	10	7,250	15	10,875
	Designing uniform	670	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
	Measuring	729	10	7,290	5	3,645	5	3,645	10	7,290	5	3,645	10	7,290	5	3,645	5	3,645	5	3,645	10	7,290
	Measuring uniform at the customer's place	676	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
	Preparing materials & equipment	622	15	9,330	15	9,330	10	6,220	10	6,220	10	6,220	10	6,220	5	3,110	5	3,110	10	6,220	15	9,330
	Making patterns	744	20	14,880	20	14,880	15	11,160	15	11,160	15	11,160	15	11,160	10	7,440	10	7,440	15	11,160	20	14,880
	Cutting cloth	735	15	11,025	15	11,025	10	7,350	10	7,350	10	7,350	10	7,350	5	3,675	5	3,675	10	7,350	15	11,025
	Overlocking	458	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290
	Sewing	613	150	91,950	90	55,170	50	30,650	60	36,780	50	30,650	60	36,780	25	15,325	25	15,325	50	30,650	120	73,560
	Finishing	420	5	2,100	5	2,100	5	2,100	5	2,100	5	2,100	5	2,100	2	840	-	-			15	6,300
	Ironing	425	25	10,625	25	10,625	15	6,375	15	6,375	15	6,375	15	6,375	10	4,250	10	4,250	15	6,375	15	6,375
	Packaging	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807
	Taking order	517	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585	5	2,585
	Adjusting	533	60	31,980	35	18,655	20	10,660	25	13,325	20	10,660	25	13,325	10	5,330	10	5,330	20	10,660	50	26,650
	Making a payment	511	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555	5	2,555
	Support activities	500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500	5	2,500
	Total Indirect Costs (Rp)		203,567		146,192		104,092		104,092		95,297		111,362		60,752		59,912		96,822		179,797	
	Cost of Revenue per Unit (Rp)		255,637		193,262		122,862		129,762		113,267		134,332		62,322		77,982		104,392		216,867	

Table 11. Calculation of the Cost of revenue of the Uniform Products in Bulk with TDABC

No.	Activity	Rate per Activity (Rp/Minutes)	Uniform Type							
			PDH Uniform		Safari		Shirt		Trousers	
			Time (Minutes)	Amount (Rp)	Time (Minutes)	Amount (Rp)	Time (Minutes)	Amount (Rp)	Time (Minutes)	Amount (Rp)
1	Direct Cost (Rp)		18,770		25,670		17,970		1,570	
2	Indirect Cost									
	a. Batch :									
	Accepting order	555	10	5,550	10	5,550	10	5,550	10	5,550
	Designing uniform	670	40	26,800	40	26,800	40	26,800	40	26,800
	Taking order	517	10	5,170	10	5,170	10	5,170	10	5,170
	Making a payment	511	10	5,110	10	5,110	10	5,110	10	5,110
	Support activities	500	30	15,000	30	15,000	30	15,000	30	15,000
	Total Indirect Cost per Batch (Rp)			57,630		57,630		57,630		57,630
	Total Indirect Cost per Unit (Rp)			1,153		1,153		1,153		1,153
	b. Unit :									
	Measuring uniform	676	5	3,380	5	3,380	5	3,380	5	3,380
	Preparing materials & equipment	622	10	6,220	10	6,220	10	6,220	5	3,110
	Making patterns	744	15	11,160	15	11,160	15	11,160	10	7,440
	Cutting cloth	735	10	7,350	10	7,350	10	7,350	5	3,675
	Overlocking	458	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290	5	2,290
	Sewing	613	60	36,780	60	36,780	50	30,650	25	15,325
	Finishing	420	5	2,100	5	2,100	5	2,100	2	840
	Ironing	425	15	6,375	15	6,375	15	6,375	10	4,250
	Packaging	807	1	807	1	807	1	807	1	807
	Adjustring	533	25	13,325	25	13,325	20	10,660	10	5,330
	Total Indirect Costs (Rp)			89,787		89,787		80,992		46,447
	Cost of Revenue per Unit (Rp)			109,710		116,610		100,115		49,170

The calculation of cost of revenue (cost to make and sell) with TDABC was used to calculate profit (loss) from each type of product produced by MSME "XYZ". The average selling price for each product is presented in table 12. Profit (loss) in Rupiah and percentage is presented in table 13.

Table 12. Average Selling Price of Each Type of Product

No.	Product	Selling Price (Rp)	Avg Selling Price (Rp)
1	Jacket	700,000 – 750,000	725,000
2	Blazer	550,000 – 600,000	575,000
3	PDH Uniform	210,000 – 250,000	230,000
4	Safari	220,000 – 280,000	250,000
5	Shirt	120,000 – 160,000	140,000
6	Blouse	150,000 – 180,000	165,000
7	Trousers	100,000 – 130,000	115,000
8	Skirt	120,000 – 150,000	135,000
9	Dress	180,000 – 250,000	215,000
10	Kebaya	200,000 – 300,000	250,000
11	PDH uniform in bulk	190,000	190,000
12	Safari in bulk	190,000	190,000
13	Shirt in bulk	100,000	100,000
14	Trousers in bulk	70,000	70,000

The selling price was determined by considering the use of additional materials and level of complexity of the sewing process according to the customer's wishes (custom made), so that the selling price for the same type of product might vary.

Table 13. Calculation of Profit (Loss) per Product Type

No.	Product	Selling Price(Rp)	Cost of Revenue(Rp)	Profit/Loss(Rp)	Profit/Loss(%)
1	Jacket	725,000	255,637	469,363	64.74
2	Blazer	575,000	193,262	381,738	66.39
3	PDH Uniform	230,000	122,862	107,138	46.58
4	Safari	250,000	129,762	120,238	48.10
5	Shirt	140,000	113,267	26,733	19.10
6	Blouse	165,000	134,332	30,668	18.59
7	Trousers	115,000	62,322	52,678	45.81
8	Skirt	135,000	77,982	57,018	42.24
9	Dress	215,000	104,392	110,608	51.45
10	Kebaya	250,000	216,867	33,133	13.25
11	PDH uniform in bulk	190,000	109,710	80,290	42.26
12	Safari in bulk	190,000	116,610	73,390	38.63
13	Shirt in bulk	100,000	100,115	-115	-0.11
14	Trousers in bulk	70,000	49,170	20,830	29.76

With TDABC, the calculated cost of revenue is the total cost (cost to make and sell) so that the profit earned is the actual operating profit of each product.

TDABC can also be used to identify each activity that is consumed by each type of cost of revenue, so that it can be seen that the working time of employees has not been maximized, which can be seen by comparing the available time capacity and the time used, presented in table 14.

Table 14. Comparison of Available Time Capacity with Time Used (Minutes)

No.	Product	Sales (Unit)	Processing Time	Total Time
1	Jacket	96	341	32,736
2	Blazer	24	246	5,904
3	PDH Uniform	720	176	126,720
4	Safari	300	176	52,800
5	Shirt	1,248	161	200,928
6	Blouse	480	186	89,280
7	Trousers	4,524	103	465,972
8	Skirt	288	101	29,088
9	Dress	96	161	15,456
10	Kebaya	84	301	25,284
11	PDH uniform in bulk	99	153	15,147
12	Safari in bulk	54	153	8,262
13	Shirt in bulk	468	138	64,584
14	Trousers in bulk	621	80	49,680
Total time used				1,181,841
Available time capacity				1,224,000
Time (minutes): over/under				42,159
Time (hours): over/under				703
Percentage of overtime (%)				3.44

The difference between the available time capacity and the time used was 42,159 minutes or 703 hours (41 working hours per person) in one year, even though the available time capacity took into account the ineffective time of 40%. The occurrence of deviation in effective time was due to the estimated time that was not suitable for each activity. However, the deviation had a relatively small percentage of 3.44%. The deviation was considered as a deviation that inflicted a financial loss and reduced operating profit amounting to Rp3,535,567 (table 15).

Table 15. Comparison between Allocated Indirect Costs and Actual Indirect Costs

No.	Product	Sales(unit)	Indirect cost per unit (Rp)	Total indirect cost (Rp)
1	Jacket	96	203,567	19,542,432
2	Blazer	24	146,192	3,508,608
3	PDH Uniform	720	104,092	74,946,240
4	Safari	300	104,092	31,227,600
5	Shirt	1,248	95,297	118,930,656
6	Blouse	480	111,362	53,453,760
7	Trousers	4,524	60,752	274,842,048
8	Skirt	288	59,912	17,254,656
9	Dress	96	96,822	9,294,912
10	Kebaya	84	179,797	15,102,948
11	PDH uniform in bulk	99	90,940	9,003,060
12	Safari in bulk	54	90,940	4,910,760
13	Shirt in bulk	468	82,145	38,443,860
14	Trousers in bulk	621	47,600	29,559,600
Total allocated indirect costs (Rp)				700,021,140
Total actual indirect costs (Rp)				703,556,707
Indirect costs (Rp): plus/minus				(3,535,567)
Percentage of indirect costs (%) - minus				0.50

IV. CONCLUSION

The case study that we did on MSME "XYZ" showed that TDABC could be applied to MSMEs for convection (sewing) services. The resulting cost of revenue indicated that all costs required to produce and sell the products (cost to make and sell) could be calculated accurately. Thus, it could be used to determine a more accurate selling price as well. So far, the selling price was determined based on an estimate which was then adjusted according to the additional materials used, level of complexity, and length of processing time. Determination of the selling price based on the estimate was not accurate and caused inaccurate profit or loss calculations as well. It also resulted in MSME "XYZ" not knowing whether the selling price was too high or too low.

In the future, MSME "XYZ" can adopt the TDABC calculation method that we had done to calculate the cost of revenue, starting with estimating all costs for the current year based on the cost data we collected and adjusting the percentage increase in costs that occurred in the current year. Existing activities also need to be evaluated regularly by adding new activities or removing activities that do not add value to the products.

By comparing the actual time used and the available time capacity, MSME "XYZ" can take advantage of the ineffective time by implementing various activities that can improve employee performance, such as attending training to increase competence and broaden knowledge about current clothing trends.

It is also recommended that MSME "XYZ" also seeks to increase the number of customer requests through marketing activities. An increase in demand will increase the use of employee time so that the rate per activity can be lowered. This will result in a decrease in the cost of revenue. Marketing activities that can be carried out include providing special prices, providing discounted prices for the provision of wholesale sewing services, and providing express sewing services.

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